

Synthesis, structural characterization, spectroscopic studies and antimicrobial activities of Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes derived from 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

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Abstract : We depict the synthesis of two new Schiff base ligands, formed by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 2-amino-5-methylpyridine or 2-amino-5-bromopyridine. All of these ligands have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral data. The molecular geometry of 2-(5-methylpyridin-2-ylimino)methyl)-6-methoxyphenol has been determined by single crystal X-ray study. It reveals that this ligand exist in phenol-imine tautomeric form in the solid state. The reaction of these ligands with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} resulted in the formation of mononuclear complexes having the general composition [ML₁·NO₃].H₂O. These complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, metal-estimation, molar conductivity, IR, UV-Visible, ESI-Mass, thermal analysis and magnetic measurements. Non-electrolytic behavior of complexes indicates the absence of counter ion. The studies indicate a square planar geometry of the metal complexes. The Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes have been tested for antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive bacteria; *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative bacteria; *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Keywords : Schiff base metal complexes, crystal structure, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Schiff bases have been widely used as ligands in the formation of transition metal complexes. Although many structures of transition metal complexes with Schiff base ligands have been determined, a relatively small number of free Schiff bases have been structurally characterized¹⁻⁶. However, knowing the structures of free Schiff base ligands could be important in view of comparison with the structure of Schiff base complexes. The Schiff bases are very important tools for the inorganic chemists as these are widely used to design molecular ferromagnets, in catalysis, in biological modeling applications, as liquid crystals and as heterogeneous catalysts⁷⁻⁹. Schiff base ligands containing various donor atoms (like N, O, S, etc.) show broad biological activity and are of special interest because of the variety of ways in which they are bonded to the transition metal ions^{10,11}. The Schiff bases of salicylaldehyde and aminopyridines have been characterized in

detail in solid state and in solution^{12,13} and proposed as highly sensitive spectrometric and spectrofluorimetric reagents for Cu^{II}^{14,15}. However, analogous heteroaromatic Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (*o*-vanillin) have not been investigated so thoroughly. The mono and bis-Schiff bases of *o*-vanillin and 2,3-diaminopyridine have been used as ionophores in a Cu^{II} selective electrochemical sensor¹⁶. These compounds as well as their metal complexes have been found to possess biological activity¹⁷. Antibacterial activity has also been reported for the ruthenium(II) complex of the Schiff base of *o*-vanillin and 2-aminopyridine¹⁸.

Results and discussion

All the ligands and their complexes are air and moisture free crystalline solids. The metal complexes are intensely colored. The metal complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents and only soluble in DMF and

DMSO. The elemental analyses data concur well with the planned formulae for the ligands and also recognized the $[ML_1(NO_3)] \cdot H_2O$ composition of the metal(II) complexes. The magnetic susceptibility of the metal complexes are equivalent to theoretical values of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The magnetic moments of the complexes were recorded at room temperature and the observed magnetic moment values for the $[Cu(MMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$ and $[Cu(BMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$ are 1.94 and 1.80 BM, respectively whereas the observed magnetic moment values for the $[Ni(MMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$ and $[Ni(BMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$ are 2.80 and 2.90 BM, respectively. These values are agreeable to spin only value. Hence observed magnetic moment for the complexes under study indicates that they have square planar configurations around metal ions. This is further supported by their electronic spectral data. The analytical and physical data of the Schiff base ligands and their complexes are shown in Table 1.

of 2927–2930 cm^{-1} is due to stretching vibrations of the $-OCH_3$ group. An IR spectrum of the ligand MMM is presented in Fig. 1.

The 1H NMR spectra of ligands were recorded in $CDCl_3$. The signal due to methyl protons (Ligand MMM) appeared as singlet at δ 2.36 ppm²¹, whereas signal due to methoxy protons appeared as singlet in the range δ 3.89–3.93 ppm. In the aromatic region, a few doublets and in few cases some overlapping doublets/multiplets are observed in the range δ 6.85–8.31 ppm. These signals are due to aryl protons of benzene/pyridine rings. The signals due to azomethine proton ($-CH=N-$) appeared as singlet at δ 9.41 ppm. Another singlet corresponding to one proton is observed in the range δ 13.92–14.00 ppm. This signal disappeared in the complexes²². The proton NMR spectrum of the Schiff base ligand MMM is shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1. The physical and analytical data of ligands and their metal complexes

Ligand or complex	Formula	M.W.	Color	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :				μ_{eff} Found/(Calcd.) (BM)
						Found/(Calcd.)				
						C	H	N	M	
MMM	$C_{14}H_{14}N_2O_2$	242	Orange	82	210	69.35 (69.41)	5.79 (5.82)	11.60 (11.56)	-	-
BMM	$C_{13}H_{11}BrN_2O_2$	307	Orange	89	192	50.90 (50.84)	3.57 (3.61)	9.09 (9.12)	-	-
$[Cu(MMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$	$C_{14}H_{15}CuN_3O_6$	385	Deep green	75	> 300	43.65 (43.69)	3.89 (3.93)	11.00 (10.92)	16.44 (16.51)	1.94 (1.73)
$[Ni(MMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$	$C_{14}H_{15}N_3NiO_6$	380	Reddish	82	> 300	44.21 (44.25)	3.93 (3.98)	11.01 (11.06)	15.39 (15.45)	2.80 (2.82)
$[Cu(BMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$	$C_{13}H_{12}BrCuN_3O_6$	447	Green	79	> 300	34.68 (34.72)	2.73 (2.69)	9.37 (9.34)	14.17 (14.13)	1.80 (1.73)
$[Ni(BMM) \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$	$C_{13}H_{12}BrN_3NiO_6$	445	Reddish	80	> 300	35.17 (35.10)	2.70 (2.72)	9.41 (9.45)	13.23 (13.19)	2.90 (2.82)

Characterization of the Schiff base ligands :

The IR spectra of the ligands show a broad band at 3410–3450 cm^{-1} due to the stretching vibrations of phenolic hydroxyl group¹⁹. The broadness is due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the phenolic group and the azomethine group. The strong band observed at 1605 cm^{-1} is assigned to the stretching vibrations of the azomethine group. Two moderately intense bands observed at 3046 and 2832 cm^{-1} , are due to aromatic and aliphatic $\nu(C-H)$, respectively²⁰. Whereas band appeared in range

The mass spectra of ligands MMM and BMM revealed the molecular ion peak at m/e 242 for the former ligand and m/e 308 for the latter ligand, which are coincident with the formula weights and support the identity of the structures²³. The mass spectrum of the ligand BMM is presented in Fig. 3. The mass spectral assignments for the ligands are shown in Table 2.

Molecular structure of ligands :

The molecular structure of Schiff base ligand MMM was determined from single crystal X-ray studies. ORTEP

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of the ligand MMM.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand MMM.

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of the ligand BMM.

Table 2. Mass spectral data of Schiff base ligands

Ligand/Complex	<i>m/z</i> (obsd.)	Assignments
MMM	225, 212, 199, 183, 169, 156, 119, 93, 78, 65	$C_{14}H_{14}N_2O^+$, $C_{13}H_{12}N_2O^+$, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2O^+$, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2^+$, $C_{11}H_9N_2^+$, $C_{10}H_9N_2^+$, $C_8H_9N^+$, $C_7H_8^+$, $C_6H_6^+$, $C_5H_5^+$
BMM	290, 278, 263, 247, 235, 212, 173, 159, 135, 106, 92, 78, 65, 51	$C_{13}H_{11}BrN_2O^+$, $C_{12}H_9BrN_2O^+$, $C_{12}H_9BrN_2^+$, $C_{12}H_9BrN^+$, $C_{11}H_{10}BrN^+$, $C_{12}H_{15}N^+$, $C_{11}H_{13}N^+$, $C_9H_{11}N^+$, $C_7H_7N^+$, $C_7H_8^+$, $C_6H_6^+$, $C_5H_5^+$, $C_4H_4^+$

diagram of this ligand with the atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 4. The crystallographic data are given in Table 3. Important bond lengths and angles for the compound are listed in Table 4. The single crystal X-ray diffraction study on this compound clearly indicates that the present has strong intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bond. The strong intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bond is evidence of the preference for the phenol-imine tautomeric form in the solid state. The hydrogen bonding geometry parameters of the ligand are also shown in Table 5.

Fig. 4. ORTEP view of the ligand MMM, showing the atom-labeling scheme. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level and H atoms are shown as small spheres of arbitrary radii.

Table 3. Crystal data and other experimental details

CCDC Number	834633
Crystal description	Orange rectangular
Crystal size	0.30 × 0.20 × 0.20 mm
Empirical formula	$C_{14}H_{14}N_2O_2$
Formula weight	242.27
Radiation, Wavelength	MoK α , 0.71073 Å
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 11.6052(4)$ $b = 4.9569(2)$ $c = 21.2962(10)$ Å $\beta = 91.318(4)^\circ$
Crystal system, Space group	Monoclinic, $P2_1/n$
Unit cell volume	1224.76(9) Å ³
No. of molecules per unit cell (<i>Z</i>)	4
Absorption coefficient	0.089 mm ⁻¹
<i>F</i> (000)	512
θ range for entire data collection	3.51 < θ < 25.00
Reflections collected/unique	11484/2131
Reflections observed ($I > 2\sigma(I)$)	1686
No. of parameters refined	215
Final <i>R</i> -factor	0.0476
$wR(F^2)$	0.1218
Goodness-of-fit	1.017
$(\Delta/\sigma)_{\max}$	-0.001 for × H131
Final residual electron density	-0.197 < $\Delta\rho$ < 0.165 eÅ ⁻³

Table 4. Selected bond lengths and angles in the ligand MMM

Bond distances (Å) with esd's in parentheses		Bond angles (°) with esd's in parentheses	
N1-C1	1.334(2)	C1-N1-C5	116.37(15)
N1-C5	1.342(2)	C6-N2-C1	121.72(15)
N2-C6	1.283(2)	C11-O2-C14	116.93(16)
N2-C1	1.414(2)	N1-C1-C2	122.73(16)
O1-C12	1.338(2)	N1-C1-N2	119.88(16)
O2-C11	1.370(2)	C2-C1-N2	117.38(15)
O2-C14	1.421(2)	N1-C5-C4	125.37(16)
C6-C7	1.447(2)	N2-C6-C7	120.73(16)
C7-C12	1.404(2)	N2-C6-H6	122.0(12)
C7-C8	1.404(2)	O2-C11-C10	125.71(16)
C10-C11	1.373(3)	O2-C11-C12	114.35(16)

Table 5. Hydrogen-bonding geometry (esd's in parentheses)

D-H...A	D-H (Å)	D...A (Å)	H...A (Å)	D-H...A (°)
O1-H1...N2	0.82	2.556(2)	1.83(3)	147(3)
C3-H3...O2 ⁱ	0.99(2)	3.571(2)	2.58(2)	178(2)

Symmetry code : (i) 1-x, 2-y, -z

Characterization of the metal complexes :

Spectroscopic studies of the metal complexes indicate that the ligands are tridentate, coordinating through the nitrogen of azomethine group, nitrogen of pyridine ring and phenolic oxygen.

The IR spectra of metal complexes show sharp band in the range 1600–1550 cm^{-1} , which is shifted to lower frequency as compared to ligand, suggesting coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal ion. The disappearance of $\nu(\text{O-H})$ shows the deprotonation of the -OH group and its subsequent coordination to the central metal atom. Two new bands observed at 578–564 and 481–470 cm^{-1} are characteristic of M–O and M–N absorptions, respectively¹⁹. The IR spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is shown in Fig. 5.

ESI-mass spectra of the complexes were recorded in solution (water : methanol = 1 : 1)^{24,25}. For the ESI-MS of the mono nuclear complexes, the peaks of complexes are consistent with the calculated isotopic distributions for the mono nuclear complexes (Fig. 6). The $[\text{Cu}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes give a parent ion peak at m/z 447 and 445, respectively. The mass spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 6.

The observed molar conductances of the metal(II) complexes in 10^{-3} M DMF solution are in the range 8–19 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$. The molar conductance values are consistent with the non-electrolytic nature for all metal complexes²⁶.

Fig. 5. IR spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 6. ESI-Mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Table 6. ESI-Mass spectral data of the complexes

Ligand/Complex	m/z (obsd.)	Assignments
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	430, 399, 322.8, 260.8, 197, 104	$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_5)]^+$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_4)]^+$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_4)]^+$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O})]^+$, $(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O})^+$, $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O})^+$
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	430, 399, 349, 319, 256, 104	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_5)]^+$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_4)]^+$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5)]^+$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_4)]^+$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O})]^+$, $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O})^+$

Electronic spectra of all the complexes were recorded in dimethylformamide (DMF). For square planar Cu^{II} , the expected transition is ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ with absorption at 450–460 nm. Due to Jahn-Teller (J-T) distortions, square planar Cu^{II} complexes give a broad absorption between 600 and 700 nm and the peak at 450–460 nm merges with the broad band, and thus only one broad band is observed²⁷. The Ni^{II} complexes showed one strong band at 435–445 nm, which is assigned to the square planar ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transition²⁸.

Thermal analyses of all the complexes were carried out by the TG-DTA techniques. The experimental results revealed that the degradation occurred in multiple stages, following a complex mechanism. Thermal behavior of all complexes can be explained as follows. In the present

investigation, heating rates were suitably controlled at $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ and mass loss followed upto 60–550 $^\circ\text{C}$. The simultaneous TG-DTG-DTA curve of the $[\text{Ni}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is presented in Fig. 7. The TG curve follows the decrease in sample mass with increase in temperature. The decomposition of the complexes undergoes in two stages. The degradation of lattice water molecule takes place in the first stage at 65–69 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 98–100 $^\circ\text{C}$ with a mass loss of 4.64% (calcd. 4.67%) and 4.73% (calcd. 4.72%), respectively²⁹. The maximum mass loss is indicated by the DTG peak at 64 $^\circ\text{C}$ in case of Cu-complex and 94 $^\circ\text{C}$ in case of Ni-complex. The maximum rate of mass loss is indicated by the DTA trace at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 92 $^\circ\text{C}$ respectively. The degradation of one $-\text{NO}_3$ molecule takes place in the second stage at 269 $^\circ\text{C}$

Fig. 7. TG-DTA thermogram of the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

and 309 °C with a mass loss of 16.05% (calcd. 16.07%) and 16.26% (calcd. 16.27%), respectively. The maximum rate of mass loss is indicated by the DTG peak at 279 °C in case of Cu-complex and 321 °C in case of Ni-complex. The maximum rate of mass loss is indicated by the DTA trace at 288 °C and 313 °C, respectively. Thermal data of the complexes are listed in Table 7.

enzyme activity of the bacterial system^{20,30}. MMM ligand and its metal complexes both show good antibacterial activity, which suggest that ligand inhibiting the enzymes of the bacterial system³¹. Antibacterial activity of the ligands and complexes were quite comparable to the standard drugs (data not shown). Antimicrobial activity data for the ligands and their metal complexes are shown in Table 8 (Fig. 8).

Table 7. Thermoanalytical data of the complexes

Complexes	TG range (°C)	DTG _{max} (°C)	DTA _{max} (°C)	Obsd. (Calcd.) Mass loss (%)	Assignments
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	65-69	64	60	4.64 (4.67)	Loss of lattice H_2O molecule
	269	279	288	16.05 (16.07)	Loss of coordinated $-\text{NO}_3$ molecule
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	98-100	94	92	4.73 (4.72)	Loss of lattice H_2O molecule
	309	321	313	16.26 (16.27)	Loss of coordinated $-\text{NO}_3$ molecule

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity of the ligands and the metal complexes were evaluated against the *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Metal complexes show better inhibition as compared to their ligands^{19,24}. BMM ligand does not show antibacterial activity. While Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of this ligand show remarkable antibacterial activity. It might be due to complexation of metal ions with Schiff base ligands. Such metal complexes might be inhibiting the

Table 8. Antibacterial activity of Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes

Ligand/Complex	Microbial species (Zone of inhibition in mm)			
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
MMM	7	10	9	9
BMM	-	1	-	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	8	3	6	4
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	15	8	10	8
$[\text{Cu}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11	7	5	4
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BMM})\cdot\text{NO}_3]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	7	6	8	6

Fig. 8. Antibacterial activities of Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes.

Experimental

Materials :

The chemicals and solvents were obtained from Spectrochem and Merck. Absolute alcohol was obtained from Baroda Chem. Industries Ltd., Baroda.

Techniques :

IR spectra ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the ligands and metal complexes were recorded using KBr discs on 8400 FT-IR Shimadzu spectrometer. GC-Mass spectra of the ligands were recorded on QP 2010 Shimadzu GCMS spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra of ligands were recorded on Bruker Avance-II 400 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and CDCl_3 as a solvent. ESI-Mass spectra of complexes were recorded VG-70S spectrometer. Electronic spectra of the metal complexes in DMF were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 19 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance of the metal complexes was determined on Systronics direct reading conductivity meter type CM-82T. A simultaneous TG/DTA was recorded on Perkin-Elmer Pyris-1 model. Elemental analysis (C, H and N) were carried out on elemental analyzer Perkin-Elmer 2400, while analysis of metals were determined by EDTA after decomposing the complexes with HNO_3 . Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were carried out by Gouy balance using $[\text{HgCo}(\text{CN})_4]$ as calibrant.

Preparation of Schiff base ligands :

Synthesis of 2-(5-methylpyridin-2-ylimino)methyl)-6-methoxyphenol [MMM] :

Equimolar (10 mmol) ethanolic solution (50 mL) of 2-

hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde and 2-amino-5-methylpyridine was refluxed for 6 h in round bottom flask. During the reflux a microcrystalline orange compound was separated, which was isolated by filtration and dried in air and finally purified by crystallizing in appropriate solvent.

Synthesis of 2-(5-bromopyridin-2-ylimino)methyl)-6-methoxyphenol [BMM] :

Equimolar (10 mmol) ethanolic solution (50 mL) of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde and 2-amino-5-bromopyridine was refluxed for 6 h in round bottom flask. During the reflux a microcrystalline orange compound was separated, which was isolated by filtration and dried in air and finally purified by crystallizing in appropriate solvent.

Preparation of metal complexes :

All the metal complexes of Schiff bases were prepared by the following method. The metal salt was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and the solution was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the corresponding Schiff bases. After the complete addition, little amount of sodium acetate was added and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. A crystalline solid was obtained, which was isolated by filtration, washed with hot water and dried in air.

Single crystal X-ray structure determination of Schiff base ligand [MMM] :

The X-ray intensity data of a well defined crystal ($0.3 \times 0.2 \times 0.2\text{ mm}$) were collected at room temperature (293 K) by using a CCD area-detector diffractometer

(Bruker AXS Inc., USA) which is equipped with graphite monochromated MoK α radiation ($\alpha = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). A total number of 11484 reflections were collected of which 1686 reflections were treated as observed ($I > 2\sigma(I)$). Data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization and absorption factors.

The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXS97³². All non-hydrogen atoms of the molecule were located from the E-map. Full-matrix least-squares refinement was carried out by using SHELXL97 software³². All the hydrogen atoms were located from a difference electron density map and their positional and isotropic thermal parameters were included in the refinement. The final refinement cycle yielded an *R*-factor of 0.0476 [$wR(F^2) = 0.1218$] for the observed data. The residual electron density ranges from -0.197 to 0.165 e\AA^{-3} . Atomic scattering factors were taken from International Tables for X-Ray Crystallography (1992, Vol. C, Tables 4.2.6.8 and 6.1.1.4). An ORTEP view of the title compound with atomic labeling is shown in Fig. 4³³.

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity of the all the ligands and complexes were evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. All strains were type strains. A young culture of each bacterial culture was prepared. Each bacterial culture was added to the sterilized medium before solidification. The media with bacteria was poured into steri-lized Petri dishes under aseptic condition. Different weights of Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes; (1 mg, 5 mg and 10 mg) were placed on the surface of the culture and incubated at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. After incubation zone of inhibitions (mm) were recorded¹⁹ (Fig. 8).

Conclusions :

IR data suggest O, N, N coordination of the ligands. The X-ray single crystal analysis of the ligand confirms the molecular structure with phenol-imine tautomeric form, which on deprotonation coordinates with M^{II} as a tridentate ligand. The TGA curves of the complexes show mass loss at $65\text{--}100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to loss of one lattice water molecule. The analytical data correspond to $[ML_1 \cdot NO_3] \cdot H_2O$ and molar conductances in DMF are consistent with nonelectrolytes. The proposed structures are depicted in Figs. 9a and 9b. Antibacterial activity

data suggest that such ligands and their metal complexes have potential antibacterial activity. Further investigation is required to explore such ligands for the industrial use.

Fig. 9a. The general structure of the Schiff base ligands.

Fig. 9b. The general structure of the Schiff base metal complex.

Supporting information available

CCDC 834633 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for the ligand (MMM). This data can be obtained free of charge at www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieval.html or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : +44-1223/336 033. E-mail : deposit@ccdc.ac.uk.

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